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THE EPIC OF ERGENEKON OR THE RETURN OF THE TURKIC PEOPLES

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ANNOTATION

The article presents the life of Gilgamesh, the oldest hero of the most ancient heroic epic, reviews of bitcoins about him, and the article tells about the results of the study of scientists on the question of whether Gilgamesh is a truly historical person

Keywords: sumerian, akkadian, Gilgamesh, Enkidu, epic, Uruk, Ashurbanipal, wiki, Wikipedia

INTRODUCTION

Gilgamesh is the most famous hero of Sumerian and Akkadian myths, and his image was copied from a real person. According to historians, the prototype could be the ruler of the city of Uruk, famous for great deeds and achievements in the XXVII century BC. He lived for 126 years, and after his death he became equated with the gods.

An epic was composed about the exploits and adventures of Gilgamesh, consisting of songs and legends. Of course, there are a lot of mythological elements and actors in them, but legends also store a lot of descriptions of historical events. What was the life of the great Sumerian hero – Gilgamesh?

Before getting acquainted with the life story of Gilgamesh, I would like to tell you about his name. Translated, it means “ancestor-hero”. Historians are aware of several epics dedicated to Gilgamesh. The most famous variation of the myth is the “Nineveh version”, created for the storage of the books of King Ashurbanipal. The uniqueness of these records is in the systematization of information. Scattered fragments of the Gilgamesh legends are combined into a coherent, unified plot that allows you to go through the path of exploits together with their main character.

In his youth, Gilgamesh was frivolous and reckless. The young ruler caused the discontent of his people. He indulged in fun all day long and often kidnapped the wives of his subjects.

People could not stand it for a long time, they prayed to the gods that they would create a worthy rival to Gilgamesh. Under the guidance of the goddess Aura, who

embodied maternal powers, a wild man was sculpted out of clay, who was named Enkidu. It was his mission to challenge Gilgamesh to a duel and win it.

While Enkidu lived in the steppe, unaware of the plans of the gods, Gilgamesh had a strange dream. In it, he saw a large sparkling stone that had fallen from heaven. He carefully took the beautiful find and brought it to his mother.

When Gilgamesh told his mother about his dream the next morning, she explained what it could mean. According to the wise woman, the dream spoke about the imminent meeting of Gilgamesh with a faithful friend, that he would become closer to his own brother.

Soon the hunters, who entered the steppe every day, informed the ruler about the appearance of a strange creature in the vastness of his possessions. The mysterious half-beast-half-man did not allow hunting, protected steppe animals and brutally dealt with people. Gilgamesh planned to lure out this “monster” with the help of a harlot, whom he sent to him. The plan worked, but once among the people, Enkidu himself turned into a man. Then Gilgamesh turned against him. But the rivals turned out to be completely equal in battle.

When it became clear that the battle could continue indefinitely, Gilgamesh and Enkidu appeared before the ruler's mother, asking her to judge them. In response, she called them her sons. Since then, two brave young warriors have become loyal comrades. Gilgamesh and Enkidu have traveled many roads together, performed many feats. Shoulder to shoulder they fought against the monster Hum-baba and won. When the goddess Ishtar sent a ferocious bull to the city of Uruk, the friends-brothers again opposed the monster.

Despite his valor and great achievements, Gilgamesh was in for grief. The gods were angry with Enkidu for killing Hum Baba. In addition, it has not fulfilled its purpose for which it was created.

According to the will of the deities, Enkidu died suddenly, leaving Gilgamesh alone. There was no limit to the ruler's grief. Unable to endure the mental pain, he went into the desert, where he wandered, asking for death for himself.

During his wanderings, Gilgamesh realized that it was only after the loss of his friend that he first thought about the fact that he himself was mortal. However, soon he began to worry about something else: why do the gods have immortality?

Following the sun god, he descended into the underworld, crossed the waters of death, and then found himself on the mysterious island where Utnapishti lived. This was the only person who managed to gain immortality.

Gilgamesh questioned Utnapishti about his secrets. As it turned out, immortality was granted to him by the gods after the Flood. Utnapishti noted that he alone, by the will of the gods, became an immortal man.

Of course, he could not grant Gilgamesh immortality, but he presented him with a valuable gift. It was a magical flower that could endow its owner with eternal youth. But even here Gilgamesh was unlucky. While he was talking to Utnapishti, a snake was crawling past. She stole a flower and, after swallowing it, shed her skin. Gilgamesh faced an eternally young reptile, and he had to return home with nothing. Nevertheless, Gilgamesh was not disappointed upon his return. Approaching his hometown, he saw the high walls surrounding the beautiful Uruk. An extraordinary pride filled the heart of the hero, because it was to him that the merit of the foundation of this place belonged.

The finale of the Gilgamesh legends seems unclear and mysterious to many researchers. In fact, the history of the ruler ends at the moment of his return to Uruk. We do not know what happened next with the ruler, what exploits he had to perform, what difficulties he got into. Despite this, I see a special meaning in the epic. The myth of Gilgamesh seems to tell us the immortality of man – not in a magic elixir or a gift from the gods. and in his affairs. It is not for nothing that the city of Uruk, built by Gilgamesh, existed for many centuries, preserving the memory of its bold and courageous ruler.

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